

Conclusions

1. Monoethylene glycol esters of cottonseed oil fatty acids, as well as glycerol triacetate (an ester of glycerol and acetic acid) were synthesized and investigated as multifunctional additives to diesel fuels.

2. It was found that monoethylene glycol esters of fatty acids of cottonseed oil, as well as glycerol triacetate, can be used as a resource-enhancing additive to diesel fuels when x is added to the straight-run diesel fraction D1 in the amount of 3.0-7.0% and 2.5- 5.0% wt. respectively.

References

1. H.R. Veliev, A.G. Talybov, Kh.Sh. Teiubov, Z.M. Aliyev. Multifunctional additives for diesel fuels based on vegetable raw materials. // Abstracts of reports

for the Russian Congress on catalysis "ROSKATALIZ". Novosibirsk city. 2011. 262 p.

1. Zhifeng L., Zhang F., Zhang Q. et al. Effects of fuel components on the antistatic performance of poly(olefin sulfone)s in hydrotreated diesel. // Petroleum processing section. 2011 Vol. 27. p. 946-951.

2. Patent USA 7468539. (B2) 2010. Diesel fuel composition / Wetzel T.D

3. Demirbas A. Comparison of transesterification methods for production of biodiesel from vegetable oils and fats // Energy Conversion and Management. 2014. Vol. 49. p. 125-130

4. Berenblyum A.S., Danyushevsky V.Ya., Katsman U.A. Obtaining motor fuels from non - edible vegetable oils and fats. // Petrochemistry. 2010. v. 50(4). With. 317-323

EFFECT OF SOLVATOTHERMAL COPPER (II) NANOOXIDE ON BURNING RATE OF PYROTECHNIC COMPOSITIONS

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Abstract

The paper presents the results of studies on the use of the solvothermy reaction as a method of introducing nano-oxide of copper (II) onto the components of pyrotechnic compositions. The first part of the present study deals with developing a procedure for depositing nCuO onto the surfaces of KNO₃, KClO₄, Ti and B by the solvothermal method using ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate. The second part of the study involves physico-chemical characterization of the modified components (KNO₃@CuO, KClO₄@CuO, Ti@CuO, and B@CuO) and testing these substances for burning rate.

Keywords: copper (II) nanooxide, solvothermal synthesis, dinitrourea salts, pyrotechnic compositions, surface modification, burning-rate modifier.

Introduction

Copper (II) nanooxide (nCuO) holds promise as a burning-rate catalyst of energy-rich systems and is applied in the development of various pyrotechnic compositions, including thermites used in compact devices [1-3]. There are studies in the literature regarding the effect of small quantities of added nCuO on the thermal stability of fire-retardants and high-energy materials components [4-8]. The nCuO additive accelerates the burning rate of energetic materials based on nitrocellulose/triethyleneglycol/ diaminoglyoxime, and ammonium dinitramide [9, 10]. Moreover, nCuO is also being extensively employed today in the other fields of science and technology. For instance, nCuO is utilized in the realm of alternative energy sources, such as solar

energy transmission and storage systems, and in various detectors and sensors [11-13]. Antibacterial properties of this compound have come into use in biotechnology, pharma and medicine [14, 15], in addition, nCuO is used to decompose chemical warfare agent simulants [16], nCuO is also applied as a catalyst in the syntheses of various chemicals [17, 18].

However, nCuO has no widespread use due to a number of difficulties and limitations:

- first, there is an insufficiently uniform distribution of nanoparticles between other particles of the composition components during mechanical mixing [19];

- second, only a limited quantity of the nano-material can be incorporated into a composition;

- third, there is a fact that nanoparticles are capable of dusting, resulting in static electricity and emergence of fire and explosion, and are therefore harmful to the human body when contacted [20-22].

The use of ultrasound to stir nanomaterials with other particles provides a better mixing but in this case, the particles of compounds and crystals of major ingredients are crushed and ground by the cavitation impact [23], further adversely affecting the ballistic performance of a charge and the burning rate

Despite the aforesaid problems, efforts are being continued in this direction at present. Therefore, a solution to the problem-free incorporation of nanomaterials into energetic system is the hot topic of the day

Because nCuO at small quantities is inserted into an energetic composite, one can consider a preliminary deposition (coating) of nCuO onto the surface of the used powder particles among the reliable methods for embedding nCuO into the composite.

This process allows nCuO particles to be obtained in a narrow size distribution range (1-15 nm). The high purity of the resulting nCuO is provided by the absence of impurities, since the synthesis reaction of nCuO from DNU proceeds straight to the end (to the N₂O and CO₂ gases), not generating intermediate and byproducts. However, this process turned out to be non-productive, as the copper salt of DNU is very well-soluble

Even though the reaction mixture contains reducing agents like ammonia and hydrogen, the resulting copper nanooxide is good quality. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) showed that the major compound content in nCuO was 100 % and the residue contained no metallic copper. The mean particle size was 13 nm [36]. It was noticed in this case that the glass flask after the experiment was coated with a transparent dark-shade film that was soluble in mineral acids (HNO₃ and HCl) to furnish the respective copper salts. This fact led us to an idea of preparing nanooxide coatings on different surfaces, including on powders. In this regard, we performed preliminary experiments to deposit nCuO onto the surfaces of Ti and B and evaluate the effect of nCuO on the burning rate of pyrotechnic compositions.

Our previous studies showed that the burning rate of a Ti@nCuO pyrotechnic composition was 0.38 mm·s⁻¹, which is 0.24 mm·s⁻¹ lower than that of a standard sample (KClO₄/Ti) and is 0.18 mm·s⁻¹ lower than that of a KClO₄/Ti/nCuO sample with the same composition prepared by mechanical stirring. A similar relationship was also observed for a KNO₃/B@nCuO composition whose burning rate was 8.88 mm·s⁻¹, which is 0.62 mm·s⁻¹ lower than that of a standard sample (KNO₃/B) and is 0.48 mm·s⁻¹ lower than that of a KNO₃/B/nCuO sample with the same composition prepared by mechanical stirring. These findings impelled us to continue the research [37].

The present study aimed to investigate the deposition of nCuO onto the surfaces of energetic materials

There is information on the deposition of nCuO onto the surface of materials such as TiO₂ that undergoes a change in photocatalytic activity [24] and fluorophosphate glasses that undergo a change in transmission cut-off [25]. It is also noted [4] that the deposition of nCuO onto substance particles modifies the decomposition kinetics of the substances. The described methods for depositing nCuO onto the surface of materials require sophisticated expensive equipment, for example, for radio-frequency magnetron sputtering [4, 9, 26-28], or require time expenditures because of multiple-repeating deposition cycles, for example, like in the successive ionic layer adsorption and reaction (SILAR) method [24, 29, 30], or require high temperatures for the synthesis of a target product from intermediates in case the hydrothermal method is employed [25, 31-34].

We previously devised a process for preparing nCuO by the thermal decomposition of the copper salt of N,N'-dinitrourea (DNU) in DMSO and DMF [35].

in aprotic and protic solvents whereby its isolation from the solution is fraught with a complete removal of the solvent in vacuo. In doing so, the yield of the target product declines. Later on, this process was improved through the replacement of the copper DNU by a complex cationic salt, ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate that is moderately soluble and well-isolatable in the crystalline state [36].

like KNO₃, KClO₄, Ti and B, and evaluate how KNO₃@nCuO, KClO₄@nCuO, Ti@nCuO and B@nCuO would influence the burning rate of pyrotechnic compositions.

Materials and Methods

Materials

The starting ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate was synthesized by the procedure reported in [36]; the physicochemical characteristics were on a par with the literature data.

Deposition of nCuO onto Ti

To a solution of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate (3 g) in DMFA (153 mL) or DMF (179 mL) (a 1:54 w/w ratio of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate to the solvent) was added Ti powder (15 g) with a particle size of < 40 μm. The whole was heated to 125–130 °C and held for 6 h with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was cooled down and the precipitate was decanted. The resultant sediment was washed with ethanol (3×50 mL) and diethyl ether (2×50 mL). The washed sediment was dried first for 4 h at room temperature and then in a vacuum oven at 120 °C for 6 h.

Deposition of nCuO onto B

To a solution of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate (3 g) in DMFA (153 mL) or DMF (179 mL) (a 1:54 w/w ratio of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate to the solvent) was added B powder (15 g) (a 1:5 w/w ratio of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate to B) with a particle size of < 40 μm.

The whole was heated to 125–130 °C and held for 6 h with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was cooled down and the precipitate was decanted. The resultant sediment was washed with ethanol (3×50 mL) and diethyl ether (2×50 mL). The washed sediment was dried first for 4 h at room temperature and then in a vacuum oven at 120 °C for 6 h.

Deposition of nCuO onto KNO₃

Into a three-neck flask equipped with a stirrer, thermometer and a reflux condenser was poured benzil alcohol (169.3 mL), afterwards ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate (3 g) (a 1:54 w/w ratio of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate to the solvent) was added and stirred until fully dissolved. Into the flask was then added KNO₃ (15 g) with a particle size of <140 μm (a 1:5 w/w ratio of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate to KNO₃). The whole was heated to 125 °C with stirring and held at 125–130 °C for 6 h. After the holding was completed, the reaction mixture was cooled down, and the precipitate was isolated from the resultant suspension by decantation. The obtained sediment was washed with ethanol (3×50 mL) and then diethyl ether (2×50 mL). The washed sediment was allowed to stand for 4–6 h and air-dried at room temperature, and was then held in a vacuum oven at 120 °C for 6 h. DTA: peak no. 1—136.5 °C (phase transition) and peak no. 2—336.2 °C (melting).

Deposition of nCuO onto KClO₄

Into a three-neck flask equipped with a stirrer, thermometer and a reflux condenser was poured benzil alcohol (169.3 mL), afterwards ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate (2 g) (a 1:54 w/w ratio of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate to the solvent) was added and stirred until fully dissolved. Into the flask was then added KNO₄ (15 g) with a particle size of <140 μm (a 1:5 w/w ratio of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate to KNO₄). The whole was heated to 125 °C with stirring and held at 125–130 °C for 6 h. Once the holding was completed, the reaction mixture was cooled down, and the precipitate was isolated from the resultant suspension by decantation. The obtained sediment was washed with ethanol (3×50 mL) and then diethyl ether (2×50 mL). The washed sediment was allowed to stand for 4–6 h and air-dried at room temperature, and was then held in a vacuum oven at 120 °C for 6 h. Phase transition peak (DTA): 307.7 °C.

Thermogravimetric analysis

The thermal stability of the samples was measured by TGA and DTA at a heating rate of 10 °C/min, in the air environment.

Pyrotechnic formulations

Formulation 1: 70 % KNO₃, chemically pure grade, GOST R No. 4217-77, particle size < 140 μm, and 30 % B (amorphous), A-brand, technical specifications No. 2112-001-49534204-2003, particle size < 40 μm.

Formulation 2: 67 % KClO₄, chemically pure grade, technical specifications No. 6-09-3801-76, particle size < 140 μm, and 33 % Ti, PTM-1 brand, technical specifications No. 14-22-57-92, particle size < 40 μm.

Processing of pyrotechnic compositions

Weighed portions of the ingredients of a pyrotechnic composition were taken to an accuracy of 0.0001 g to comply with the formulation. The weighed ingredients were stirred in a laboratory mixer.

Burning-rate measurement

The burning rate was measured using cylinder-shaped specimens 10 mm wide, extruded with a force of 20 kg/mm². The burning front passage was recorded by ionization detectors. The time of the burning front passage between the detectors was recorded on an oscillograph with a sampling frequency of 50 kHz.

Results and Discussion

Copper (II) nanooxide was deposited onto the surface of the substance (KNO₃, KClO₄, Ti and B) by solvothermal treatment of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate in organic solvents. The deposition procedure for copper (II) nanooxide involved the selection of a solvent first. First of all, it must be a high-boiling solvent that does not evaporate at 125–130 °C and nor solubilize the compound to be modified; as the solvent, we chose DMF, DMSO and benzyl alcohol. The reaction mixture should necessarily be stirred, and it is desirable that the substances being coated be permanently suspended. This has a bearing on the uniform coating quality. The coating process itself took place when ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate began to decompose, with the reaction mixture changing the color from blue to black. The color of the isolated compounds was also found to be distinct from the initial, and it was especially noticeable for the KNO₃ (c) and KClO₄ (d) samples (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Specimens before and after being coated with $n\text{CuO}$: titanium (a), boron (b), potassium nitrate (c), and potassium perchlorate (d)

The prepared specimens ($\text{KNO}_3@\text{CuO}$, $\text{KClO}_4@\text{CuO}$, $\text{Ti}@\text{CuO}$, и $\text{B}@\text{CuO}$) were further used to make pyrotechnic charges to be tested for burning rate.

The burning-rate measurements were performed on charges representing a set of pressed elements whose butt ends were facing each other, as shown in Fig. 2. The sample was initiated by an ignition pyro-

technic element **1**, and then a stabilizing pyrotechnic element **2** made of the same pyrotechnic composite as the basic elements **3** was employed to equilibrate the burning rate and reach the regime. Between the butt ends of the basic elements were placed ionization detectors **4** under supplied direct current (no more than 3 V), which respond to the transmission of the current-conductive ionized field of the burning front.

Fig. 2. A schematic of burning-rate measurement: 1. an ignition pyrotechnic element; 2. a stabilizing pyrotechnic element; 3. basic pyrotechnic element; and 4. ionization detector

The data were compared with those of pyrotechnic compositions fabricated from the starting unmodified components. The results of the comparative tests are illustrated in Figs 3 and 4.

Fig. 3. The effect of the modified component on the burning rate of a B/KNO₃ pyrotechnic blend

It is seen in Fig. 3 that the burning rate increased from 8.69 mm·s⁻¹ (B/KNO₃) to 10.3 mm·s⁻¹ for B@nCuO/KNO₃ (a ~18.5 % increment). At the same time, the modification of B/KNO₃@nCuO resulted in an increase in the burning rate to 10.57 mm·s⁻¹ (a ~21.7 % increment). The modification of all the components (B@nCuO/KNO₃@nCuO) of the pyrotechnic

composition provided a burning-rate increase to 11.73 mm·s⁻¹ (a ~35 % increment). It can be seen from the findings that nCuO incorporated into the B/KNO₃ pyrotechnic composition led to a catalytic effect on the burning rate. It was noted that the catalytic activity was higher in the samples whose formulation consisted of the modified potassium nitrate.

Fig. 4. The effect of the modified component on the burning rate of a KClO₄/Ti pyrotechnic blend

The results depicted in Fig. 4 demonstrate that nCuO deposited onto surface of the ingredients of the KClO₄/Ti pyrotechnic blend had an inhibitory action on the burning rate. For instance, KClO₄@nCuO diminished the burning rate from 2.15 mm·s⁻¹ to 1.85 mm·s⁻¹ (a ~ 14 % decrement), while the modified titanium (Ti@nCuO) reduced the burning rate to 1.3 mm·s⁻¹ (a ~ 39.5 % decrement). A greater inhibition of the burning rate was observed for the pyrotechnic composition whose components were all modified

(KClO₄@nCuO/Ti@nCuO), up to 1.18 mm·s⁻¹ (a ~ 45.1 % decrement).

The inhibition process of the burning rate is not natural for copper oxide, as it is known to be a burning-rate catalyst [17, 18], as also corroborated in our case of the B@nCuO/KNO₃@nCuO composition and modifications thereof (Fig. 3).

It can be speculated that the inhibition of the burning rate might be attributed to the decomposition temperature of potassium perchlorate because potassium

perchlorate in the $\text{KClO}_4/\text{nCuO}/\text{Ti}$ system is a less stable ingredient and hence a change in the decomposition temperature (to give off oxygen) can be observed after nCuO is embedded into the system. We attempted

to explore this process by using DTA and TGA. For instance, Fig. 5 displays DTA and TGA patterns for pure KClO_4 and $\text{KClO}_4/\text{nCuO}$.

Fig. 5. Thermal processes on DTA and TGA diagrams: a) KClO_4 , b) $\text{KClO}_4/\text{nCuO}$

It is seen in Fig. 5(a) that the DTA graph for KClO_4 has two peaks, these are an endothermic peak of the phase transition near 308 (307.68) °C and a peak with the melting onset near 580 °C, in agreement with [38].

The DTA thermogram for $\text{KClO}_4/\text{nCuO}$ also shows an endothermic peak of the phase transition at 307.03 °C and two melting peaks at 537.49 °C and 564.1 °C. A double melting peak is explainable by the heterogeneous KClO_4 for the first peak and by the melting of the main sample at 564.1 °C (Table 1). It should be noted in this case that the melting onset of the first

peak concurs with the decomposition onset of the $\text{KClO}_4/\text{nCuO}$ sample (TGA, Fig. 5(b)). The weight of the sample residue at 587.4 °C (Table 1) is 52.92 %, which is equivalent to a 98.7 % yield of the theoretical content of KCl (53.62 %) generated from KClO_4 . It can be seen from the TGA thermogram (Fig. 5(b)) that KClO_4 completely decomposes at 587.4 °C. It should be noted that 97.8 % of the sample remains for pure KClO_4 at 587.4 °C.

Thermogravimetric examination of samples of potassium nitrate Fig.6 showed no significant changes.

Fig. 6. Thermal processes in the DTA and TGA thermograms: a) KNO_3 and (b) KNO_3/nCuO

The DTA (Fig. 6(b)) graph for KNO_3/nCuO shows variations in the phase transition point rising to 136.25 °C, when compared to pure KNO_3 (133.46 °C), and in melting point rising to 336.23 °C (335.73 °C for

KNO_3 , 333.8 °C [39]). It should be noted herewith that the decomposition point of KNO_3 in KNO_3/nCuO is also shifted towards a temperature rise to 555.02 °C (548.55 °C) (Fig. 5(a))

Table 1.

TGA and DTA results of potassium nitrate and potassium perchlorate samples.

Sample name	Onset, °C	Peak, °C	Endset, °C	Thermal effect, J/g	Weight loss, %
KNO_3	131,8	133,5	140,0	-237,7	-6,7
	334,2	335,7	338,8	-351,0	-4,9
KNO_3/nCuO	132,1	136,5	152,4	-253,0	-1,6
	333,6	336,2	338,8	-367,6	-5,5
$\text{KClO}_4/\text{nCuO}$	304,4	307,03	311,4	-406,4	-2,0
	509,0	537,49	543,4	-512,1	-17,1
	552,2	564,1	587,4	729,4	-28,0
KClO_4	304,2	307,68	311,3	-400,4	-4,4

Summarizing the obtained DTA/TGA results, we can say that nCuO deposited on the surface of KClO₄ exhibits the properties of a catalyst for the rate of decomposition of KClO₄, but this fact cannot explain the inhibition of the rate of combustion of the composition KClO₄@nCuO/Ti. It is quite possible that in this case, the metal, Ti, can influence the inhibition of the combustion rate. While deposited nCuO on the surface of KNO₃ leads to a shift in the phase transition temperatures and melting points by several degrees higher.

Conclusions

1. The burning-rate tests performed for the KClO₄@nCuO/Ti@nCuO and B@nCuO/KNO₃@nCuO pyrotechnic blends demonstrated that nCuO deposited by the solvothermal method has a 45.1 % inhibitory effect on the burning rate of KClO₄/Ti and a 35.1 % catalytic effect on B/KNO₃.

2. The DTA and TGA studies showed that nCuO deposited onto the KClO₄ surface by the solvothermal method presents with properties of a decomposition-rate catalyst of KClO₄, with KClO₄ being observed to completely decay (98.7 %) to KCl at 587.4 °C, while 97.8 % of the pure sample remained at the same temperature. For KNO₃@nCuO (DTA), the phase transition point was noted to rise to 136.25 °C as compared with pure KNO₃ (133.46 °C), and the melting point rose to 336.23 °C (335.73 °C for KNO₃, 333.8 °C as per literature data). It should be noted herewith that the decomposition point of KNO₃ in KNO₃@nCuO is also shifted towards a temperature rise up to 555.02 °C (548.55 °C for pure sample)

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References

1. Glavier L., Taton G., Ducéré J.-M., Baijot V., Pinon S., Calais T. Estève A. Rouhani M., Rossi C. Nanoenergetics as pressure generator for nontoxic impact primers: Comparison of Al/Bi₂O₃, Al/CuO, Al/MoO₃ nanothermites and Al/PTFE. *Combustion and Flame*, 2015; 162 (№ 5): 1813–1820. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2014.12.002>.
2. Taton G., Lagrange D., Conedera V., Renaud L. Micro-chip initiator realized by integrating Al/CuO multilayer nanothermite on polymeric membrane. *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering*, 2013; Vol. 23 (№ 10): 105009. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0960-1317/23/10/105009>
3. Ru C., Wang F., Xu J., Dai J., Shen Y., Ye Y., Zhu P., Ruiqi S. Superior performance of a MEMS-based solid propellant microthruster (SPM) array with nanothermites. *Microsystem Technologies*, 2017; Vol. 23 (№ 8): 3161–3174. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00542-016-3159-x>
4. Xiang Zhou, Ying Zhu, Zhipeng Cheng, Xiang Ke, Kaiwen Shi, Kaili Zhang Preparation of Cyclotrimethylenetrinitramine-Copper Oxide Core-Shell Particles and Their Thermal Decomposition Kinetics. *Propellants, Explosives, Pyrotechnics*, 2019; Vol. 44: 1368-1374. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prep.201900093>

5. Hao Wang, Tao Guo, Wen Ding, Miao Yao, Xiang Fang, Jia-xing Song, The Effect of CuO on the Thermal Behavior of the High-Energy Combustion Agent of the Al/MnO₂ System. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, 2019; Vol. 2019 Article ID 4536268. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4536268>
6. Pandas H.M., Fazli M. Preparation and Application of La₂O₃ and CuO Nano Particles as Catalysts for Ammonium Perchlorate Thermal Decomposition. *Propellants Explos. Pyrotech.*, 2018; 43: 1096–1104. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prep.201800036>.
7. Bingwang Gou, Yong Kou, Yubing Hu, Guangpu Zhang, Hu Guo, Lei Xiao, Fengqi Zhao, Hongxu Gao, Wei Jiang, Gazi Hao Effect of Nano-Copper Chromite on the Thermal Decomposition and Combustion of AP-Based Solid Propellants. *Propellants Explos. Pyrotech.*, 2022; 47(10): e202200087. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prep.202200087>
8. Yinon Yechezkel, Ishai Dror, Brian Berkowitz, Catalytic degradation of brominated flame retardants by copper oxide nanoparticles, *Chemosphere*, 2013, Volume 93(1): 172-177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.05.026>.
9. Mirzajani V., Nazarpour-Fard H., Farhadi K., Ghobadian A. Copper Oxide Nano-Catalyst Incorporated TEGDN/NC/DAG Propellants: Thermal Behaviors and Kinetics. *Propellants Explos. Pyrotech.*, 2022; 47: e202100364. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prep.202100364>.
10. Fujisato, K., Habu, H., Miyake, A., Hori, K. and Vorozhtsov, A.B. Role of Additives in the Combustion of Ammonium Dinitramide. *Propellants, Explosives, Pyrotechnics*, 2014; 39: 518-525. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prep.201300148>.
11. Singh J., Rawat M. A Brief Review on Synthesis and Characterization of Copper Oxide Nanoparticles and its Applications. *Journal of Bioelectronics and Nanotechnology*, 2016;1(1): 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.13188/2475-224X.1000003>.
12. Aparna Y, Rao K.V., Subbarao P.S. Synthesis and characterization of CuO nano particles by novel sol-gel method. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Environment Science and Biotechnology*, 2012; Vol. 48: 156-160.
13. Kannaki K., Ramesh P.S., Geeta D. Hydrothermal synthesis of CuO nanostructure and their characterization. *Ins. J Sci Eng Res*, 2012; 3: 1-4.
14. Masri A., Brown D., Smith D., Stone V., Johnston H. Comparison of In Vitro Approaches to Assess the Antibacterial Effects of Nanomaterials. *Journal of Functional Biomaterials*. 2022; 13(4): 255. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jfb13040255>.
15. Ding, J.; Liu, J.; Chang, X.B.; Zhu, D.; Lassen, S.B. Exposure of CuO nanoparticles and their metal counterpart leads to change in the gut microbiota and resistome of collembolans. *Chemosphere* 2020, 258: 127347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.127347>.
16. Verma M., Gupta V.K., Dave V., Chandra R., Prasad G.K. Synthesis of sputter deposited CuO nanoparticles and their use for decontamination of 2-chloroethyl ethyl sulfide (CEES). *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2015; 438: 102-109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2014.09.060>.

17. Elkhshab R.A., Nayl A.A., Badawy E., El Malah T. Nano-copper Oxide as Catalyst for Click Reactions. *J. Chem. Chem. Eng.*, 2016; 10: 341-346. <https://doi.org/10.17265/1934-7375/2016.07.005>.
18. Shestakova E.O., Il'yasov S.G., Shchurova I.A., Glukhacheva V.S., Il'yasov D.S., Zhukov E.E., Bryzgalov A.O.; Tolstikova T.G.; Gatilov Y.V. Investigation of 1,4-Substituted 1,2,3-Triazole Derivatives as Antiarrhythmics: Synthesis, Structure, and Properties. *Pharmaceuticals*, 2022; 15: 1443. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph15121443>.
19. Wei D., Dave R., Pfeiffer R. Mixing and Characterization of Nanosized Powders: An Assessment of Different Techniques. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 2002; 4: 21-41. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020184524538>.
20. Bo Liu, Kaili Xu, Yuyuan Zhang, Ji. Ge Powder Explosion Inhibitor Prepared from Waste Incinerator Slag: Applied to Explosion Suppression of Oil Shale Dust Explosion *Applied Sciences*, 2022; 12: 1034. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12031034>.
21. Saurabh Sonwani, Simran Madaan, Jagjot Arora, Shalini Suryanarayan, Deepali Rangra, Nancy Mongia, Tanvi Vats, Pallavi Saxena Inhalation Exposure to Atmospheric Nanoparticles and Its Associated Impacts on Human Health: A Review. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, 2021; 3: 10.3389/frsc.2021.690444.
22. Strauch, B.M., Niemand, R.K., Winkelbeiner, N.L., Hartwig A. Comparison between micro- and nanosized copper oxide and water soluble copper chloride: interrelationship between intracellular copper concentrations, oxidative stress and DNA damage response in human lung cells. *Part Fibre Toxicol*, 2017; 14: 28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12989-017-0209-1>.
23. Vinay Raman, Ali Abbas, Wenting Zhu Particle Grinding by High-Intensity Ultrasound: Kinetic Modeling and Identification of Breakage Mechanisms. *AIChE Journal*, 2011; 57(8): 2025 - 2035. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.12415>.
24. Lebedev V.A., Sud'in V.V., Kozlov D.A., Garshev A.V. Photocatalytic properties of nanocrystalline TiO₂ modified with CuO and WO₃. *Russian nanotechnologies*, 2016; 11: 27-34.
25. Kolobkova E.V., Ba Min Dinh, Kochetkova A.S. Formation of nanostructured CuO film on the surface of fluorophosphate glasses. *Scientific and technical bulletin of information technologies, mechanics and optics*, 2017; 17 (1): 46-51.
26. Mahendra Goddati, Reddappagari Malathi, Kedhareswara Pasupuleti, A. Lakshminarayana, Merum Dhananjaya, Nunna Guruprakash, O. Hussain, Alain Mauger, Christian Julien. RF Sputter-Deposited Nanostructured CuO Films for Micro-Supercapacitors. *Applied Nano*, 2021, 2: 46-66. <https://doi.org/10.3390/applnano2010005>.
27. Pecquenard, B.; Le Cras, F.; Poinot, D.; Sicardy, O.; Manaud, J.P. Thorough characterization of sputtered CuO thin films used as conversion material electrodes for lithium batteries. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2014; 6: 3413-3420. <https://doi.org/10.1021/am4055386>
28. Purusottam-Reddy, B.; Sivajee-Ganesh, K.; Hussain, O.M. Growth, microstructure and supercapacitive performance of copperoxide thin films prepared by RF magnetron sputtering. *Applied Phys. A*, 2016; 122(2): 128. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-015-9588-z>.
29. Patil A., Patil M., Lohar G., Jadhav S., Fulari V. Supercapacitive properties of CuO thin films using modified SILAR method. *Ionics*, 2017; 23: 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11581-016-1921-9>.
30. K. Mageshwari, R. Sathyamoorthy Physical properties of nanocrystalline CuO thin films prepared by the SILAR method *Materials Science in Semiconductor Processing*, 2013; 16 (2): 337-343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mssp.2012.09.016>.
31. Patil A.S., Lohar G.M., Fulari, V.J. Structural, morphological, optical and photoelectrochemical cell properties of copper oxide using modified SILAR method. *J Mater Sci: Mater Electron*, 2016; 27: 9550-9557. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-016-5007-2>
32. Jha, Vinay Synthesis of nanosized copper oxide particles using hydrothermal treatment. *Nep. J. Integrated Sciences*, 2012; 2: 42-46.
33. Sackey J., Nwanya A.C., Bashir A.K.H., Matinise N., Ngilirabanga J.B., Ameh A.E., Coetsee E., Maaza M. Electrochemical properties of Euphorbia pulcherrima mediated copper oxide nanoparticles, *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 2020; 244: 122714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2020.122714>.
34. Khatavkar S.N., Sartale S.D. Superior supercapacitive performance of grass-like CuO thin films deposited by liquid phasedeposition. *New, J. Chem.*, 2020; 44: 6778-6790. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9NJ04201F>.
35. Il'yasov S.G., Kazantsev I.V., Til'zo M.V., Sakovich G. V., Zaikovskii V. I., Prosvirin I.P., Tuzikov F.V. A New Method of Preparing Copper Oxide from Dinitrourea Copper Salt. *Zeitschrift für anorganische und allgemeine Chemie*, 2014; Vol. 640, Is. 11: 2132-2138. <https://doi.org/10.1002/zaac.201400311>.
36. Rudakov E.V., Il'yasov A.S., Tilzo M.V., Il'yasov S.G., Kuznetsov V.M., Potekae A.I. Preparation of ammonium bis(N,N'-dinitrourea)cuprate (II) and copper (II) nanooxide. *Polzunovskiy vestnik*, 2016; 4 (1): 118-123.
37. Zhukov E.E., Kazantsev I.V., Il'yasov S.G. Solvatothermolysis as a method for modification of pyrotechnical composition components. *South Siberian Scientific Bulletin*, 2020; 6 (34): 112-116. <https://doi.org/10.25699/g3339-2379-0977-m>.
38. Lee, Jinn-Shing & Hsu, Chung-King & Jaw, Kuen-Shan. (2001). The thermal properties of KClO₄ with different particle size. *Thermochimica Acta*. 367-368. 381-385. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6031\(00\)00691-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6031(00)00691-2).
39. Beneš, O. & Konings, R.J.M. & Wurzer, S. & Sierig, M. & Dockendorf, A.. (2010). A DSC study of the NaNO₃-KNO₃ system using an innovative encapsulation technique. *Thermochimica Acta - THERMOCHIM ACTA*. 509. 62-66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2010.06.003>.